

Special Issue
**Special Issue of European Journal of Tourism Research
“Smart Tourism Destinations: Advancing Theory and Practice”**
Guest Editors:
Luisa Errichiello¹ and Roberto Micera²

¹ National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development (IRISS), Via G. Sanfelice, 8 - 80134 Naples (Italy), E-mail: l.errichiello@iriss.cnr.it

² National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development (IRISS), Via G. Sanfelice, 8 - 80134 Naples (Italy), E-mail: r.micera@iriss.cnr.it

The Smart Tourism Destination (STD) is an emerging paradigm for optimizing the use of touristic resources, enhancing tourism experiences, increasing destination competitiveness and improving residents' quality of life (Gretzel *et al.*, 2015; Lopez de Avila, 2015). The STD is built on a shared platform of state of art technologies that: integrates information on tourism businesses and use of resources; interconnects dynamically all the stakeholders to share relevant knowledge; manages big data and data analytics tools for decision-making and tourism experience co-creation (Wang *et al.*, 2013; Lamsfus *et al.*, 2015; Del Chiappa, Baggio, 2015; Buhalis, Amaranggana, 2013, 2015). To realize a STD, it is essential to embrace a holistic approach that takes into account complementary dimensions to technology, namely human and social capital, leadership, innovation and sustainable development (Boes *et al.*, 2015).

This Issue aims to identify new perspectives of analysis, relevant concepts and practices along with opportunities for future research.

By integrating smart tourism development and urban management, Della Corte, D'Andrea, Savastano and Zamparelli propose a classification system to strategically position city-destinations based on two variables: the adoption of a systemic approach and the degree of experiential innovation.

Liburd, Nielsen and Heape's research shows how tourism co-design can be leveraged to understand the dynamic and processes of smart tourism practices and social enactment, going beyond a mere technical, data driven and service-dominant logic.

Through the analysis of a tourism municipality in Gran Canaria Island, Hernández-Martín, Rodríguez-Rodríguez and Gahr explain how the delimitation of functional areas with tourism relevance can help destination managers to improve decision-making processes in the context of STDs.

Frikha, Mhiri and Gargouri elaborate a method for measuring trust between online friends and, deeping the Smart-TMT, a recommendation system, they show the value of social network web applications to improve the level of personalization in destination offer.

Relying on an analysis of best practices relating to the application of ICTs in cultural heritage sites, Buonincontri and Marasco analyze how these technologies can enhance all the experience dimensions. The paper demonstrates the value of adopting a multi-stage and multi-dimensional perspective of cultural heritage experience at tourism destination in exploiting smart technologies.

We would like to thank Dr Stanislav Ivanov, Editor-in-chief of the European Journal of

Tourism Research for providing us with the opportunity to edit this special issue. We would also wish to thank the reviewers for putting time and efforts in reviewing the papers and providing valuable comments on the manuscripts.

References

- Boes, K., Buhalis, D. & Inversini, A. (2015). Conceptualising smart tourism destination dimensions. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism* (pp. 391-403). Springer International Publishing.
- Buhalis, D. & Amaranggana, A. (2014). Smart tourism destinations. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism* (pp. 553-564). Springer International Publishing.
- Buhalis, D. & Amaranggana, A. (2015). Smart tourism destinations enhancing tourism experience through personalisation of services. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism* (pp. 377-389). Springer International Publishing.
- Del Chiappa, G. & Baggio, R. (2015). Knowledge transfer in smart tourism destinations: analyzing the effects of a network structure. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 4(3), 145-150.
- Errichiello L., Micera R. (2015), Smart Tourism Destination Governance, in Spender JS, Shiuma G., Albino V. (Eds.), *Culture, Innovation and Entrepreneurship: connecting the knowledge dots*, (pp. 2179-2191), Proceedings of IFKAD 2015 – International Forum on Knowledge Asset Dynamics, 10-12 June, Bari. ISBN: 978-88-96687-07-9; ISSN 2280-787X.
- Gretzel, U., Sigala, M., Xiang, Z., & Koo, C. (2015). Smart tourism: foundations and developments. *Electronic Markets*, 25(3), 179-188.
- Gretzel, U., Werthner, H., Koo, C., & Lamsfus, C. (2015). Conceptual foundations for understanding smart tourism ecosystems. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 50, 558-563.
- Koo, C., Gretzel, U., Hunter, W. C., & Chung, N. (2015). Editorial: The Role of IT in Tourism. *Asia Pacific Journal of Information Systems*, 25 (1), 99-104.
- Lamsfus, C., & Alzua-Sorzabal, A. (2013). Theoretical framework for a tourism internet of things: Smart destinations. *TourGUNE Journal of Tourism and Human Mobility*, 0, 15-21.
- Lamsfus, C., Martín, D., Alzua-Sorzabal, A., & Torres-Manzanera, E. (2015). Smart tourism destinations: An extended conception of smart cities focusing on human mobility. In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism* (pp. 363-375). Springer International Publishing.
- Lopez de Avila, A. (2015). *Smart destinations: XXI century tourism*. Paper presented at the ENTER2015 conference on information and communication technologies in tourism, Lugano, Switzerland.
- Wang, D., Li, X. R., & Li, Y. (2013). China's "smart tourism destination" initiative: A taste of the service-dominant logic. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 2(2), 59-61.
- Xiang, Z., Tussyadiah, I., & Buhalis, D. (2015). Special Issue: Smart destinations. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 4(3), 143-201.
- Zhu, W., Zhang, L., & Li, N. (2014) Challenges, Function Changing of Government and Enterprises in Chinese Smart Tourism. In Z. Xiang & I. Tussyadiah (Eds.), *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism* Dublin: Springer.